

**SERVICE QUALITY AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS
A FIRST-CHOICE DECISION FRAMEWORK OF A TOURIST
DESTINATION IN SELECTED RESORT HOTELS IN PALAWAN**

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ABSTRACT

Service quality (SQ) is one of the main determinants of customer satisfaction (CS), and a focal topic of researchers and practitioners alike across all industries. This research aims to determine the relationship and trends between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction (SQCS), identify the gaps, and formulate strategies. The study utilized a quantitative research design employing the descriptive-correlational research method. Data in this research was acquired from guests from five resort hotels located in Palawan. To address this objective, the researcher analyzes the effect of SQ dimensions (Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Empathy, and Assurance) on CS factors (Ambience, Value-Added, and Hospitality). Multiple regression analysis denotes increases of 34.0% 21.2%, and 20.0% on the extent of the effect attributed to SQ dimensions on CS factors, respectively. Results obtained indicate that Tangibility, Assurance, and Responsiveness have a positive impact, whereas Empathy and Reliability do not. By establishing the CASA WISH (House of Wish) first-choice decision framework of a tourist destination, The researcher postulates that Communication, Attention, Safety, Attitude, Wellness, Information, Security, and Health are key elements

in prioritizing, improving, and reinforcing the significant positive relationship between service quality – the consistent process of understanding, addressing, implementing, fulfilling, and adhering to the client’s needs and demands, without overstepping the transaction’s provisions to the entity’s discretion, and customer satisfaction - the mind, heart, and spirit of marketing which manifests a business philosophy and strategy, leading to loyalty and profitability of resort hotels.

Keywords: *Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Tourism, Hospitality, Services Marketing*

INTRODUCTION

The hospitality and tourism industry is a significant domain for scholarly and practitioner inquiries and has flourished rapidly and steadily over the years (Al Masud et al., 2023; Bhuvaneshwari & Maruthamuthu, 2024). Thus, it is generally regarded not only as a source of domestic income but also as a major contributor in generating foreign exchange which benefits the economy. The sector encompasses many enterprises, including hotels, restaurants, travel agencies, and tour operators. Developed countries and developing countries continue to develop and improve the quality of their country's tourism. (Amin et al, 2019).

While numerous studies have explored the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry, there are only a few that have been conducted based on the specific context of resort hotels in the Philippines. The latest WTTC’s Economic Impact Report (EIR) also takes a forward look at the sector with the global tourism body forecasting that the Philippines' Travel & Tourism contribution to GDP will grow by 6.7% over the next decade, exceeding the expected country's overall economy average growth rate of just 5.6%, accounting for 21.4% of the whole economy by the year 2032.

According to Fu (2023), a hotel defines the section of the service industry that deals with guest accommodations or lodgings. Eurostat (2020) on the other hand states that a hotel is a key component of a tourist establishment that provides furnished accommodation and a range of additional facilities and services as a paid service. Hotels are recognized as one of the sectors with the highest excessive consumption of resources in the tourism industry (Mak & Chang, 2019). The success of a hotel is not only measured by the physical quality of the building but also by its ability to provide a pleasant and satisfying stay for every guest (Ariani et al.,2024). A hotel may consist of either one or more building structures, including accommodation and amenities. Lvov & Komppula (2024) opine that even though accommodation is regarded as the major product of a hotel, the experience throughout the stay may vary for every customer depending on the hotel’s facilities, services, and offerings.

A resort hotel is a luxury facility primarily used by vacationers for a getaway. Resort hotels are considered a vital element of the tourism industry because they satisfy the

guests' most essential need: accommodation (Varsanis et al., 2019). In the Philippine setting, resort hotels are typically near natural tourist attractions, such as beaches and seashores, mountains, or spas. Usually, resorts operate only on a seasonal basis. However, most of them now operate throughout the year.

The intertwining relationship between hospitality and tourism reveals that while lavish resort hotels are one of the requirements of their respective target market, it is also of utmost importance that the destination is accessible with various offerings in terms of gastronomical, recreational, and must-see wonders. Several destinations and resort hotels are crafting specific marketing campaigns to attract their primary target market by highlighting their unique features and services. Awareness of customer needs and expectations is of utmost importance in such a demanding service landscape, achieving high levels of Customer satisfaction through service quality is crucial to gaining a competitive advantage.

Achieving and establishing customer satisfaction (Hereinafter referred to as "CS") in association with rendering exemplary (Hereinafter referred to as "SQ") is recognized, as the crux, epitome, and *raison d'être* of any service business to differentiate their identity, retain customers, and attract new ones at the same time, to achieve and meet the industry quality requirements and benchmarks, survive intense competition, increase productivity, establish competitive advantage, as well as increase the profit margins. This research aims to examine the various latest trends in Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction (Hereinafter referred to as "SQCS") research, identify and close the gaps, and formulate strategies.

SQ has become a major area of attention and investigation to practitioners, managers, and researchers alike because it is a complex concept, which contains a large range of dimensions that may vary from sector to industry (Al Masud et al., 2023; Nunkoo et al., 2020). SQ emanates from associating an abstract and elusive concept determined by the customer's knowledge and understanding (Chan et al., 2022; Rauf et al., 2024a). SQ encompasses all economic activities whose results are not products in physical form or construction (Mashur et al., 2019; Santos de Oliveira & Caetano, 2019). SQ is the extent of excellence to which a service rendered meets the expectation and satisfaction discerned by a client during their engagement with a service provider or utilization of a service (Fatma & Kumar, 2024; Zygiaris et al., 2022). SQ has been extensively studied as it is one of the tools many organizations use as a strategy to differentiate them from their competitors (Ishak & Saraih, 2021). SQ plays a pivotal role in enabling companies to adapt to evolving customer needs and ensure business sustainability. SQ is one of the crucial aspects of every business wherein different companies compete in this area, which acts as a differentiator considering the same sector or business type (Afroj et al., 2021; Alam & Mondal, 2019) and must be unceasingly maintained by all employees in the company (Surahman et al., 2020).

Hamadziripi & Daniels (2023) allude that SQ is assessed and evaluated in service organizations such as hotels, as they interact with a service representative. Evaluation

of the SQ from the consumer aspect includes the feelings of the guests that appear before, during, and after using the service, which are the expectations and the perception of the service of the consumer (Gallarza et al., 2019). SQ is formed by a comparison between the ideal and the perception of the performance dimension of quality (Clara et al., 2022; Dethan et al., 2020). SQ controls how well a firm's level of service meets customer demand (Gross, Ingerfurth, & Willems, 2021; Padlee, et al., 2020). Gaunker & Gaonkar (2021) further add that SQ evaluates how well-delivered services meet customer expectations. Likewise, Apfiasari & Rimawan (2023) state that SQ is the desired degree of perfection, and how to manage that perfection to maximize client needs. According to Indrasari (2019), SQ is the fulfillment of customer needs and desires accompanied by accuracy in conveying desires to balance the customer's desires. Abror et al. (2020) further argue that the SQ is determined by its compliance with the customer's requirements and expectations, and the better the fit, the higher the CS.

SQ refers to the timely and sincere service to the customer and how the customer values such service (Ali, 2021; Ali & Anwar, 2021; Faraj et al., 2021; Andavar & Ali, 2020). Customers are most concerned about the SQ (Arlen, 2022). SQ is the customer's attitude towards a service, formed by a series of both successful and unsuccessful service experiences (Susanti & Juliani, 2021). Customers view responsive SQ as a long-term service. (Faisal, 2024). According to Zeithaml et al. (2020), customers consider SQ as an essential determinant factor of the repurchase to many customers. As such, the researcher defines SQ as the consistent process of understanding, addressing, implementing, fulfilling, and adhering to the client's needs and demands, without overstepping the transaction's provisions to the entity's discretion. SQ serves as the firm's statement to the customer regardless of whether they enjoyed the provided service or they did not. A key challenge for businesses in managing SQ is how to measure it accurately and effectively (Guo et al., 2024). According to Zeithaml et al. (2020), customers consider SQ an essential determinant factor of repurchase to many customers.

CS is a multidimensional, multivariate, and extensive notion. Academics and marketing practitioners have long been interested in studying and analyzing numerous elements of CS. According to Aripin & Agusady (2024), The importance of CS cannot be ignored in the modern business context. The researcher defines CS as the mind, heart, and spirit of marketing which manifests a business philosophy and strategy. CS is the voluntary choice of an individual or entity to utilize, purchase, or consume a certain product and or service offered by an enterprise that exudes the feeling of fulfillment of obligations, expectations, wants, and needs. Puspasari et al. (2022) state that CS is the key to retaining customers. Also, execution and excellence of service reflect CS.

The hotel industry is vast. As such, numerous studies measure CS in this area (Cherdouh et al., 2022; Kim & Kim, 2022; Xiao et al., 2021). The American Society for Quality (ASQ) defines CS as a measurement that determines how customers are delighted with a company's products, services, and capabilities. This statement aligns with that of Javed et al. (2021). Hitherto, CS is an assessment of a product or service related to the actual level of pleasure felt when used, consumed, or experienced by a

customer (Matsuoka, 2022). Whether or not CS arises is determined by the behavior seen whenever customer needs are met after using the product or service (Ghazmahadi et al., 2020; Khasanah et al., 2021; Mariam et al., 2021). CS is a gauge and comparison of how well a firm's product or services lives up to the customer's needs and expectations. (Jahan & Shahria, 2022; Zhong & Moon 2020). CS is determined by acquired experience, with the assessment of the feeling of pleasure or disappointment people experience when they compare the perceived outcomes with their expectations (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2022; Ghosh, 2020). According to Ahmed et al. (2023), CS refers to the assessment or the degree of compliance with customers' expectations regarding a service or product delivered by an organization. CS is the consumer's response to the service by comparing it with what is expected (Susilowati & Yasri, 2019). Customers can assist management in determining which service areas most require improvement by participating in surveys of CS (Nunkoo et al., 2020). Chattopadhyay (2019) states that CS is the best indicator of how the business looks in the future. CS has a positive and significant direct effect on repurchase intention and profitability (Sutriani et al., 2024; Ginting et al, 2023; Yunus et al., 2023; Situmorang et al., 2023).

CS plays a key role and is widely considered and acknowledged by hotel management as a helpful factor in a successful business strategy to increase sales and raise profits (Taha, 2019). CS is a critical success factor for the hospitality industry because it indicates the level of relationship between the firm and the customer. Also, CS is not a universal phenomenon because it is a combination of a product and service. In the hotel industry, user satisfaction is associated with meeting or exceeding client expectations when using a product or service (Gamage et al., 2022). According to Malik et al. (2020), CS provides insights into enhancing SQ and business excellence in the hotel industry. CS serves as an indicator to analyze whether the guests return and repeatedly visit a particular hotel when they perceive a satisfied or dissatisfied service. Information obtained from measuring CS provides invaluable insights and prerequisites to understanding the customer's needs, preferences, and expectations, as well as the implementation of continuous improvements or innovations to products and services (Nafi'ah, 2023).

The link between SQ and CS through empirical investigations is foundational, as it aligns with and consistently supports the expectancy-disconfirmation theory (Gazi et al., 2024). SQ plays a pivotal role in CS (Singh et al., 2023). The importance of SQ measurement is often underscored by its direct correlation with CS (Assaker et al., 2020). Tourist destinations must assess SQ and identify the factors influencing CS to remain competitive in the global tourism market.

In addition to the location itself, SQ and its impact on CS are the three critical successful factors for the successful operation of a resort hotel business (Grönroos, 1990; Parasuraman et. al., 1988), which are necessary requisites to attract a steady influx of clientele in a tourist destination. However, all three aforementioned factors are interrelated as the SQ and the location are also the main sources of customer complaints which can contribute to a decrease in CS (Nguyen et al., 2024). Although the factors influencing CS change constantly, SQ remains as one of its main determinants (Song et

al., 2022). SQCS are important determinants of competitive advantage, success in service, and intent to revisit (Cheng et al., 2021; Koc, 2021; George et al., 2019).

SQ intends to provide and fulfill the desires and needs of customers towards CS, which is influenced by features and perceptions of SQ, via the rendered service. CS. However, the exact nature of the relationship between SQCS has been layered with complexity that the former and the latter have been used to describe each other constantly interchangeably changed. The interpretations and roles of these two elements have varied considerably. While SQ and CS may share a lot of similarities, they are not the same because SQ plays the role of the more specific judgment as a cognitive concept, whereas CS is a much broader evaluation with both cognitive and affective concepts. Henceforth, an established underlying link remains therein between them, regardless of the circumstances in interpretations and points of view.

SQ plays a phenomenal role in building a strong and positive relationship with CS in the service industry (Safirda & Salim, 2024; Gonu et al., 2023). The outcome of CS identifies the individual contribution made by each dimension of SQ (Perdomo-Verdecia, et al., 2024). SQ is integral for ensuring high CS and competitive advantage in the hotel industry (Viskovic, 2024). SQ is surely and highly related to CS (Saputro et al., 2020) such that a direct relationship is often found as SQ improves the probability of CS as higher CS will also result from increased SQ (Sutriana et al., 2024; Halika & Kharisma, 2024; Prum, Sovang, & Bunteng, 2024; Putra & Sobari, 2024; Safirda & Salim, 2024; Spio-Kwofie et al., 2024; Syarvina, & Rahma, 2024; Veas-González et al., 2024; Indajang et al., 2023; Pimić et al., 2023; Raza, 2023; Rosyad et al., 2023; Alfajar et al., 2021; Chayomchai, 2021; Dam & Dam, 2021; Saputro et al., 2020; Leninkumar, 2019; Myo et al., 2019). However, other studies (Akmal, Panjaitan, & Ginting, 2023; Dsouza & Sharma 2022; Tibrani 2020; Vu, Pham & Nguyen 2020), among others, which hereby contradict and conclude that SQ does not affect, or has no significant effect, or has a weak relationship to CS. However, the evaluation and ranking of the significance of the SQ dimensions is not uniform and may be easily affected by customer heterogeneity (Park et al., 2021).

Based on a gap model, Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988, 1991), SERVQUAL is the most widely used method generously used and implemented in SQ studies that pertain to hospitality and tourism sectors for instance, hotels (Suyaman et al., 2024; Aladwan et al., 2022; Kalavathy & Swapna, 2019; Chin & Tsai, 2013). With some customizations, the underpinning theory for this study is the RATER Model which aims to empirically examine service quality and customer satisfaction resulting from good service efficiency and must maintained permanently if the firm can meet customer expectations. The assessment takes into account the opinions and attitudes of guests, indicating a customer-centric approach to evaluating service quality (Inversini et al., 2020). It is valid, reliable, and widely applicable across organizations in the service sector.

1. Reliability – The consistent, dependable, and accurate fulfilment in implementation and delivery of the promised offered service.

2. Assurance - the ability to build, guarantee, and deliver trust, security, and confidence in customers through employees' knowledge and courtesy.
3. Tangibility – delivery of appearance and existence of physical structures, surroundings, facilities, amenities, equipment, personnel, and communication materials.
4. Empathy – caring, prompt, accurate, and individualized quality service to each customer, thus making them feel extra valued and special.
5. Responsiveness – the willingness to help customers in providing good, quality and fast delivery of service.

According to Choi & Chu (2001), resort hotels' CS involves many elements, such as the ambiance of the hotel, the hospitality of the service provided to the customer, and value-added. According to Sim, Mak, & Jones (2006), this method was designed to confirm the antecedents (ambiance and hospitality) and the consequence of CS (value added) in the resort hotel industry.

1. Ambiance – the setting, character, atmosphere, and mood of a business location.
2. Hospitality – the cordial reception, welcome, and entertainment of guests and strangers of diverse social backgrounds and cultures charitably, socially, or commercially with kind and generous liberality, into one's space to dine and/or lodge temporarily. (Morrison & O' Gorman, 2006).
3. Value-Added – the manner and method that a firm's products and / or services gauges and communicates its worth towards customers.

Research Questions

Specifically, it dwelled on the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the occupants in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age,
 - 1.2 Sex,
 - 1.3 Civil Status,
 - 1.4 Education,
 - 1.5 Job Classification,
 - 1.6 Purpose of Visit,
 - 1.7 Income per month?
2. To what extent is the effect of service quality evaluated by its (Primary Target Market) occupants in the selected resort hotels in Palawan in terms of:
 - 2.1 Tangibility
 - 2.2 Reliability
 - 2.3 Responsiveness
 - 2.4 Assurance
 - 2.5 Empathy
3. To what extent is the effect of customer satisfaction evaluated by its (Primary Target Market) occupants in the selected resort hotels in Palawan in terms of:
 - 3.1 Ambience
 - 3.2 Added Value
 - 3.3 Hospitality

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the quantitative research method. According to Malhotra (2011), quantitative research design is based on numerical character aimed at qualifying the data through statistical analysis. Quantitative research relies on measurement and inference procedures that are relatively independent of the researcher's interpretations, which has given it a reputation as an impartial and reproducible approach for evaluating the scientific worth of management theories (Luoma & Hietanen, 2024).

To address the research questions, this study will employ the descriptive-correlational research design which is used in research studies that aim to provide static pictures of situations, as well as establish the relationship between different variables (McBurney & White, 2009). It also explains the relationship of SQCS in the resort hotel industry which requires the collection of quantitative data. Both primary and secondary data sources were used to ask research questions. The supervisor's views were elicited to prepare the questionnaire, and then the research questionnaire was revised.

Data in this research was acquired from guests who have visited and stayed in 5 resort hotels located in Palawan. Purposive sampling is used in this study as it provides characteristics based on rigorous and stringent pre-defined criteria which is vital in the research process (Thomas, 2022). According to Obilor (2023), purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique wherein the researcher selects only those subjects that satisfy the objectives of the study based on the researcher's conviction. The participants were selected if they met either, any, or all the following criteria:

1. They are guests interviewed by the hotel staff while they are checked in at the premises of the said resort hotels
2. They are guests who have made room reservations at the selected resort hotels; an
3. They are currently utilizing the services provided by the resort hotel.

According to the study of Singh-Ackbarali & Maharaj (2014), testing a product's acceptability or liking requires a sample size of 75 to 150 consumers. However, only 130 complete questionnaires were returned, which were then encoded and analyzed, but are still considered to have fulfilled the required sample size.

Table 1 lists the general characteristics of the respondents who completed the survey questionnaire. The findings revealed that most of the respondents were female (57.69 percent), widowed (59.00 percent), aged between 31 and 40 (43.00 percent), had a postgraduate degree (43.08 percent), worked as self-employed (31.54 percent), and earned between 600 and 1000 USD per month (31.0 percent).

Table 1: Demographic Profiles of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	55	42.31
	Female	75	57.69
Age	Under 20 years old	23	17.69
	21 to 30	26	20.00
	31 to 40	43	33.08
	41 to 50	18	13.85
	Above 51 years old	20	15.38
Civil Status	Single	12	9.23
	Married	32	24.62
	Widow	59	45.38
	Separated	27	20.77
Education	High School Graduate	12	9.23
	College Level	19	14.62
	College Graduate	43	33.08
	With Postgraduate	56	43.08
Job Class	Self-employed	41	31.54
	Civil Servant	39	30.00
	Retired	38	29.23
	Worker	12	9.23
Purpose of Visit	Recreation/Entertainment	42	32.31
	Business	25	19.23
	Historical/Cultural Trip	30	23.08
	Health	33	25.38
Monthly Salary	Under 300 USD	13	10.00
	300-600 USD	27	20.77
	600-1000 USD	46	35.38
	Over 1000 USD	44	33.85
	Total	130	100.00

Source: Authors

The first step of the measurement testing process is the reliability test. One method of measuring reliability is through internal consistency which refers to the degree of inter-correlation among items that comprise the measure or summated scale (Flynn et al., 1990). In this study, Cronbach's alpha (α) was determined to measure the reliability or consistency of the instrument used in the study and is the average of the correlation coefficient of each item with each other item (Streiner et al., 2015; Christmann & Van Aelst, 2006; Cronbach & Meehl, 1955). Cortina (1993, p.98) described Cronbach's alpha as one of the most important and pervasive statistics in research involving test construction and use. Table 2 below shows the result of reliability and the widely accepted measure of internal consistency.

Table 2: Results of Reliability - Cronbach's alpha

VARIABLES	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha	Mean	SD
Service Quality (SQ)	25	0.81	4.23	0.83
Customer Satisfaction (CS)	24	0.76	4.44	0.71
Overall	49	0.84	4.33	0.78

Source: Authors

The following are the alpha coefficients of the research variable; SQ ($\alpha = 0.81$, $n = 25$), CS ($\alpha = 0.76$, $n = 24$), and Overall ($\alpha = 0.84$, $n = 49$). These results further demonstrate the dependability of all variables, reinforcing the reliability of our measurement instrument, all of which met the guidelines proposed by Nunnally (1978). Cronbach's alpha values were above the threshold values (0.6-0.7) for all groupings indicating that the operational statements are significantly related to the respective construct, and 0.8 or greater is a very good level in most research studies in social sciences. (Canavan, Delahaye & Sekaran, 2000; Hair, 2020; Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994; Pallant, 2011; Phan & Matsui, 2012; Ursachi et al., 2015).

The initial measures were refined and pre-tested to enhance the validity and accuracy of the questionnaire and justify, examine, and establish the relationship between SQ and CS in the Philippine (specifically Palawan) resort hotels. The customized RATER model consists of five dimensions (Tangibility, Reliability, Reliability, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy) in 25 developed expressions. Whereas the partially adopted CS factor and antecedent model consists of three proposed factors (Ambiance, Added Value, and Hospitality) in 24 developed constructs and indicators (Sim et al., 2006).

Closed-end questionnaires (A Five-point Likert's Rating scale) were used to assess attitudes views, and expressions wherein it has two utmost poles and a neutral option, with the classifications as follows: Very large extent with a value of 5, Large extent with a value of 4, Some extent with a value of 3, Little extent with a value of 2, and Very little extent with a value of 1.

RESULTS

Kline (2023) considers missing data a serious problem.

Verbal Interpretation and Range of the Five-point Likert-type scale

Table 3 lists each scale item measured and evaluated using a five-point Likert-type scale.

Table 3: Verbal Interpretation and Range of the Five-point Likert-type scale.

Verbal Interpretation	Value	Range
Very Large Extent	5	4.21-5.00
Large Extent	4	3.41-4.20
Some Extent	3	2.61-3.40
Little Extent	2	1.81-2.60
Very Little Extent	1	1.00-1.81

Source: Authors

Extent of Effects of SQ to the occupants in selected resort hotels in Palawan

Table 4 lists the summary of the extent of the effect of SQ on occupants in selected resorts and hotels in Palawan.

Table 4: Extent of Effects of SQ to the occupants in selected resort hotels in Palawan

Dimensions	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Tangibility	4.11	Large Extent
Reliability	4.21	Very Large Extent
Responsiveness	4.26	Very Large Extent
Assurance	4.21	Very Large Extent
Empathy	4.35	Very Large Extent
OVERALL MEAN	4.23	Very Large Extent

Source: Authors

Extent of Effects of CS to the occupants in selected resort hotels in Palawan

Table 5 lists the summary of the extent of the effect of SQ on occupants in selected resorts and hotels in Palawan.

Table 5: Extent of Effects of CS to the occupants in selected resort hotels in Palawan

Dimensions	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Tangibility	4.11	Large Extent
Reliability	4.21	Very Large Extent
Responsiveness	4.26	Very Large Extent
Assurance	4.21	Very Large Extent
Empathy	4.35	Very Large Extent
OVERALL MEAN	4.23	Very Large Extent

Source: Authors

Multiple Regression Analysis on the Extent of the effect of SQ dimensions on Ambiance CS Factor

Table 6 lists the utility of the predictive model as significant, the value of R squared ($R^2 = 0.340$) which denotes a 34.0% increase in the Ambiance factor of CS is attributed to SQ. Since the F-test generated from the ANOVA table measures the probability of chance departure from a straight line ($F=12.749$, $p<0.001$), which explains that we have enough evidence to show that the Ambiance factor of CS is significantly affected by SQ.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis on the Extent of the effect of SQ dimensions Ambiance on CS Factor

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sigma
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.30	0.45		5.06	0.00
Reliability	0.20	0.07	0.29	2.79	0.01
Assurance	0.19	0.07	0.27	2.82	0.01
Tangibility	0.18	0.05	0.29	3.32	0.00
Empathy	0.22	0.09	0.20	2.36	0.02
Responsiveness	-0.26	0.08	-0.35	-3.35	0.00

R square = 0.340

F = 12.749

df₁ = 5

df₂ = 124

p-value = 0.000

Multiple Regression Analysis on the Extent of the effect of SQ dimensions on Value-Added CS Factor

Table 7 lists the utility of the predictive model as significant, the value of R squared ($R^2 = 0.212$) which denotes a 21.2% increase in the Value-Added CS factor is attributed to SQ. Since the F-test generated from the ANOVA table measures the probability of chance departure from a straight line ($F=6.86$, $p<0.001$), which explains that we have enough evidence to show that the Value-Added CS factor is significantly affected by SQ.

Table 7: Multiple Regression Analysis on the Extent of the effect of SQ dimensions on Value-Added CS Factor

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sigma
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.27	0.49		6.65	0.00
Reliability	0.09	0.08	0.13	1.20	0.23
Assurance	0.20	0.07	0.30	2.85	0.01
Tangibility	0.21	0.06	0.35	3.71	0.00
Empathy	-0.07	0.10	-0.06	-0.66	0.51
Responsiveness	-0.17	0.08	-0.23	-2.01	0.05

R square = 0.212
 $F = 6.686$
 $df_1 = 5$
 $df_2 = 124$
 p -value = 0.000

Source: Authors

Multiple Regression Analysis on the Extent of the effect of SQ dimensions on Hospitality CS Factor

Table 8 lists the utility of the predictive model was significant, the value of R squared ($R^2 = 0.200$) which denotes a 20.0% increase in the Hospitality CS factor is attributed to SQ. Since the F-test generated from the ANOVA table measures the probability of chance departure from a straight line ($F=6.20$, $p<0.001$), which explains that we have enough evidence to show that the Hospitality CS factor is significantly affected by SQ.

Table 8: Multiple Regression Analysis on the Extent of the effect of SQ dimensions on Hospitality CS Factor

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sigma
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.52	0.37		9.60	0.00
Reliability	-0.02	0.06	-0.03	-0.27	0.79
Assurance	0.08	0.05	0.16	1.52	0.13
Tangibility	0.19	0.04	0.43	4.44	0.00
Empathy	0.04	0.08	0.05	0.56	0.57
Responsiveness	-0.08	0.06	-0.14	-1.21	0.23

R square = 0.200
F = 6.200
df₁ = 5
df₂ = 124
p-value = 0.000

Source: Authors

Multiple Regression Analysis on the Extent of Effect of Each SQ Dimension on Each CS Factor

Table 9 lists the utility of the predictive model was significant, the value of R squared ($R^2 = 0.200$) which denotes a 20.0% increase in the Hospitality CS factor is attributed to SQ. Since the F-test generated from the ANOVA table measures the probability of chance departure from a straight line ($F=6.20, p<0.001$) explains that we have enough evidence to show that the Hospitality CS factor is significantly affected by SQ.

Table 9: Multiple Regression Analysis on the Extent of effect SQ dimensions on Value-Added CS Factor

SQ	CS		
	Ambience	Added Value	Hospitality
	Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant
Reliability	0.00	0.23	0.79
	Significant	Significant	Not Significant
Assurance	0.00	0.01	0.13
	Significant	Significant	Significant
Tangibility	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant
Empathy	0.02	0.51	0.57
	Significant	Significant	Not Significant
Responsiveness	0.01	0.05	0.23

Source: Authors

Results of the Research Hypothesis

Table 10 lists the results of the research hypothesis. Results indicated a strong relationship and the extent of the effect of SQ dimensions and CS factors. Therefore, this study is of utmost importance in understanding the underlying factors to create, give, and attain exemplary SQCS in service organizations, hospitality, and tourism sectors, both from academic and practical perspectives. Furthermore, the findings reveal that each dimension of SQ has varying degrees of impact on each factor of CS in this study.

The Tangibility SQ dimension has a positive and significant effect on all indicated CS factors and has emerged as the most significant attribute and predictor of tourists' standards for hotels in Palawan. On the other hand, the Ambience CS Factor has received a positive and significant effect on all SQ dimensions.

Despite having the lowest mean rating, the Tangibility SQ dimension emerged in this study as the most important to tourists in the selected resort hotels in Palawan. According to Zeithaml et al. (2006), Tangibility is used by organizations to impart image and quality. Many previous studies found Tangibility to be one of the significant SQ dimensions affecting CS (Nguyen et al. 2020; Mena et al. 2020; Haron et al. 2020; Al Khattab & Aldehayyat, 2011; Fah & Kandasamy, 2011; Juwaheer 2004; Mei et al., 1999). However, in some cases, it does not have any significant effect (Dedeoğlu & Demirer, 2015, Hu et al., 2019).

Compared with the purchase of tangible products, customers tend to feel a higher level of risk when purchasing services such as tourism and hospitality. (Birinci et

al., 2018; Koc, 2013; Ryu et al., 2022). Every company aims to give its customers unique, positive, and unforgettable first-hand impressions, which makes them more likely to return in the future (Delgado & Ballester, 2004).

The next most important SQ dimensions are Responsiveness and Assurance, respectively. While they do not have a significant impact on the Hospitality CS Factor, both SQ dimensions played a significant role in shaping the Ambiance and Value-Added CS factors. Assurance builds trust and confidence in customers via employees' knowledge and courtesy (Ojo, 2010). Saeed et al (2021), Aleshaiwy (2015), and Douglas & Connor (2003) further testify that the Assurance SQ dimension has the maximum influence on CS. Whereas Sangpikul (2022b), Minh et al., (2015), Shekarchizadeh et al. (2011), and Karunaratne & Jayawardena, (2010) have determined that the Responsiveness SQ dimension has the maximum influence on CS.

The findings of this study echo that of Ahmad et al (2019), who affirmed that there is a significant and positive relation between the Tangibility, Assurance, and Responsiveness dimensions of SQ on CS. On the other hand, the Reliability and Empathy SQ dimensions do not have a significant impact on CS. The results show that the guests in the selected resort hotels in Palawan play significant importance on some aspects of SERVQUAL dimensions such as Tangible, Responsiveness, and Assurance rather than factors such as Reliability and Empathy. Hence, to improve overall CS, businesses in this research undertaking must strive to continuously raise the standard of their services (Almonawer et al., 2023).

According to the respondents, the Empathy and Reliability SQ dimensions are the least important, which may not significantly affect CS and its factors (Ambiance, Value Added, and Hospitality). The Reliability SQ dimension demonstrates the organization's ability to perform the rendered service dependably and accurately every time. If the customers feel they receive individualized and quality attention, they will likely return to the company and do business there again.

The Empathy SQ dimension involves individualized customer attention and communication required to understand the needs and attention of the guest (Bahadur et al., 2018). The Empathy, Reliability, and Assurance SQ dimensions stand out as the predominant significantly impacting CS (Khan & Fasih, 2014; Kaura et al., 2012; Jayasundara et al. 2009; Negi, 2009; Aga & Safakli, 2007; and Ismail et al. (2006). Anas, 2024; Yeong et al., 2022; Mouzaek et al., (2021), Minh et al (2015), Hossain (2012), have determined that the Empathy SQ dimension has the maximum influence on CS. Reliability is the ability to perform the service dependably and accurately (Dabholkar et al., 1996). The Reliability SQ dimension has the maximum influence on CS (Ayvaz-Çavdaroğlu, et al., 2024; Shresra, 2021; Marković, S., & Janković).

The results of the study thus revealed and confirmed many previous researchers' recognition that SQ not only has a significant influence and impact, but is also related to, and may have a positive correlation to improve CS (Manurung & Ningsi, 2024; Suyaman, 2024; Jasin & Firmansyah, 2023; Shafiq, et al., 2023; Abdullah, Prabhu, & Othman, 2022; Brucal et al., 2022; Sumarsid & Paryanti, 2022; Yorulmaz, &

Taş, 2022; Zygiaris, et al., 2022; Dandis et al., 2021; Dewi et al., 2021; Hassan & Salem, 2021; Nurwahyudi & Rimawan, 2021; Pan & Ha, 2021; Segoro & Elvira, 2021; Shava 2021; Supriyanto et al., 2021; Ulfy et.al, 2021; Gaudenzi et al., 2020; Goumairi et al., 2020; Hutagaol & Erdiansyah, 2020; Islam et al., 2020; Mosimanegape et al., 2020; Nguyen et al., 2020; Murad et al., 2019; Othman et al., 2019; Susilawaty et al., 2020; Salleh et al., 2019; Setiawan et al., 2019; Setvarko, 2019; Shafiq, Mostafiz & Taniguchi, 2019; Sujay, 2019). This means that better SQ leads to better the CS. However, amongst the 15 hypotheses of this research, only 9 were accepted. Table 10 below shows the hypothesis of this research.

Table 10: Results of the Research Hypothesis

No.	Hypothesis	Results	Actions
H ₁ :	SQ for Reliability > CS for Ambience	P=0.01	Accepted
H ₂ :	SQ for Reliability > CS for Value-Added	P=0.23	Rejected
H ₃ :	SQ for Reliability > CS for Hospitality	P=0.79	Rejected
H ₄ :	SQ for Assurance > CS for Ambience	P=0.00	Accepted
H ₅ :	SQ for Assurance > CS for Value-Added	P=0.01	Accepted
H ₆ :	SQ for Assurance > CS for Hospitality	P=0.13	Rejected
H ₇ :	SQ for Tangibility > CS for Ambience	P=0.00	Accepted
H ₈ :	SQ for Tangibility > CS for Value-Added	P=0.00	Accepted
H ₉ :	SQ for Tangibility > CS for Hospitality	P=0.00	Accepted
H ₁₀ :	SQ for Empathy > CS for Ambience	P=0.02	Accepted
H ₁₁ :	SQ for Empathy > CS for Value-Added	P=0.51	Rejected
H ₁₂ :	SQ for Empathy > CS for Hospitality	P=0.57	Rejected
H ₁₃ :	SQ for Responsiveness > CS for Ambience	P=0.00	Accepted
H ₁₄ :	SQ for Responsiveness > CS for Value-Added	P=0.05	Accepted
H ₁₅ :	SQ for Responsiveness > CS for Hospitality	P=0.23	Rejected

Source: Authors

DISCUSSION

Conclusions

This paper contributes to the theoretical orientation of tourism SQCS in Palawan's resort hotel industry literature by determining some major SQ levels. This study also affirmed the RATER and CS Factor and Antecedent models model five tourism SQ dimensions, namely: Reliability, Assurance, Tangibility, Empathy, and Responsiveness, all of which comprise the criteria tourists use to evaluate the SQ of resort hotels in Palawan.

The results of the study show that most of the respondents are aged 31 – 40. For sex demographics, the number of female respondents is higher compared to male respondents. When this research was undertaken, women were generally more willing to participate in surveys compared to males. Most of them are widowed/widower, had a postgraduate degree, worked as self-employed, and earned between 600 and 1,000 USD monthly.

Results indicated a strong relationship and the extent of the effect of SQ dimensions and CS factors. Therefore, this study is of utmost importance in understanding the underlying factors to create, give, and attain exemplary SQCS in service organizations, hospitality, and tourism sectors, both from academic and practical perspectives. Furthermore, the findings reveal that each dimension of SQ has varying degrees of impact on each factor of CS in this study.

The guests in the selected resort hotels in Palawan concurred that they have experienced a 34.0 % increase of CS in Ambience, a 21.2% increase in the Value-Added, and a 20.0% increase in the Hospitality across all SQ dimensions, particularly in Tangibility. Despite having the lowest mean rating, its extent of effect across all factors of CS has given it the most important dimension of SQ. The Tangibility dimension of SQ emerged in this study as the most important to tourists in the selected resort hotels in Palawan. According to Zeithaml et al. (2006), Tangibility is used by organizations to impart image and quality. Nguyen et al. (2020); Mena et al. (2020); Al Khattab & Aldehayyat (2011); Fah & Kandasamy (2011); Juwaheer (2004); and Panda & Das, (2014) have determined that the Tangibility SQ dimension has the maximum influence on CS.

Compared with the purchase of tangible products, customers tend to feel a higher level of risk when purchasing services such as tourism and hospitality. (Birinci et al., 2018; Koc, 2013; Ryu et al., 2022). Every company aims to give its customers unique, positive, and unforgettable first-hand impressions, which makes them more likely to return in the future (Delgado & Ballester, 2004).

Assurance and Responsiveness respectively are the second most important dimensions of SQ. Assurance builds trust and confidence in customers via employees' knowledge and courtesy (Ojo, 2010). Saeed et al (2021), Aleshaiwy (2015), and Douglas & Connor (2003) testify that the Assurance SQ dimension has the maximum influence on CS. Whereas Anas (2024), Sangpikul (2022b), Minh et al., (2015), Shekarchizadeh et al.

(2011), and Karunaratne & Jayawardena, (2010) have determined that the Responsiveness SQ dimension has the maximum influence on CS.

The findings of this study echo that of Ahmad et al (2019), who affirmed that there is a significant and positive relation between the Tangibility, Assurance, and Responsiveness dimensions of SQ on CS. On the other hand, the Reliability and Empathy SQ dimensions do not have a significant impact on CS. The results show that the guests in the selected resort hotels in Palawan play significant importance on some aspects of SERVQUAL dimensions such as Tangible, Responsiveness, and Assurance rather than factors such as Reliability and Empathy.

According to the respondents, the Empathy and Reliability dimensions of SQ are the least important, and they may not significantly affect CS and its factors (Ambiance, Value Added, and Hospitality). The Reliability SQ dimension demonstrates the organization's ability to perform the rendered service dependably and accurately every time. If the customers feel they receive individualized and quality attention, they will likely return to the company and do business there again. On the other hand, according to Theresa & Bangun (2017), the Empathy SQ dimension is a surety in determining SQCS and involves building a captivating customer relationship via effective communication and sincere attention required to fulfill the guests' needs and wants, therefore establishing CS (Anas, 2024; Bahadur et al., 2018).

The Empathy, Reliability, and Assurance SQ dimensions stand out as the predominant significantly impacting CS (Khan & Fasih, 2014; Kaura et al., 2012; Jayasundara et al. 2009; Negi, 2009; Aga & Safakli, 2007; and Ismail et al. (2006). Hossain (2012), Minh et al (2015), Mouzaek et al., (2021), and Anas (2024) have determined that the Empathy SQ dimension has the maximum influence on CS. Reliability is the ability to perform the service dependably and accurately (Dabholkar et al., 1996). The Reliability SQ dimension has the maximum influence on CS (Ayvaz-Çavdaroğlu, et al., 2024; Shrestha, 2021; Markovic & Raspor, 2010)

Likewise, hotel managers should constantly improve customers' perceptions of SQ delivery to upgrade their performance. All the aforementioned factors and strategies will not be successfully implemented without proper integrated service marketing communication. It is also important to give attention to SQ dimensions which scored a high scale level in analysis to improve them more and work on strongly on those which scored lower scale values to improve them.

Guests were satisfied with the availability of convenient location, comfortable and up-to-date furniture and fixtures, appealing interior and exterior decoration, neat and presentable staff, and conducive to rest to the CS factors of Ambiance, Value-Added, and Hospitality, respectively.

Guests were impressed with the willingness of the staff to provide prompt service, availability to respond whenever service is needed and required, flexibility in accommodating to their demands as much as possible, learning and adapting to needs for

continuous improvement of hospitality operations, and giving vital information whenever needed.

Guests felt assured by being safe and secure throughout their stay, knowing that the staff knew the surrounding areas to the best of their abilities, imparted confidence with the knowledge and skills of the staff by being unceasingly friendly and respectful.

Guests appreciated the abilities of the staff in their accurate and timely rendering of service, the hotel reservation system, and data privacy and confidential record-keeping procedures in ensuring safety and security. Guests also appreciated the staff listening to their complaints and feedback, operating hours, and a healthy menu.

However, both the Empathy and Reliability SQ dimensions have a gap with CS factors, particularly Value-Added and Hospitality. To illustrate, Individual attention to each guest and understanding each guest's specific needs and requirements, as well as transport requirements, were huge deal breakers to the guests. Although all three indicators received only a large extent in the survey, they have a huge impact on affecting the research hypothesis. Overall, both dimensions received the highest mean rating with respect to the extent of the effects of SQ.

Palawan resort hotels should focus on improving the Empathy and Reliability dimensions of SQ to understand the gaps and improve them to win over the competition. The researcher recommends that hotel managers should set the proper SQ standards and support staff in availing resources and facilities (trained staff, proper system) as per the dimensions of SQ to satisfy their customers by providing them utmost attention and concern. They also must minimize the communication obstacles in cooperation with the staff to establish an organizational culture that complies with the rules and standards of SQ.

Even though they scored highly in these fields, continuous improvements in these areas must be constantly implemented and formulated to attain the highest level of agreement which is a "Very Large Extent", with their overall rendition of service. Moreover, they still must improve in other fields, especially Empathy and Reliability. Nonetheless, the consumer has acknowledged receiving high SQ. Another important result of the study is the positive effect of CS on the intention to recommend. Therefore, the higher the CS, the higher the intention to recommend (Şen et al., 2024).

Tourist destinations, including Palawan resort hotels, should also embody and prioritize health and wellness. Health is considered as the balanced relationship of a person (in this case customers and employees alike) with his or her environment. Misselbrook (2014) states that health can be conceptualized as living well in the presence or absence of illness. Whereas wellness is considered the positive component of health, one that is simply beyond non-sickness. Dunn (1959) opines that wellness is a direction of progress toward a higher functional potential. The ideal of ancient Greek philosophy of a healthy mind in a healthy body can only be achieved if people establish internal harmony with the physical and the social environment. In the case of hotels as a segment in the tourism sector, it is to weave the empathy dimension of SQ through the Value-Added CS factor.

As such, a tourist destination should also give out a symptom of health and wellness tourism through its local diet. Palawan resort hotels can take advantage of this by hiring Chefs who are experts in Filipino and European pescetarian and vegan cuisine options. Even though most of the clientele of Palawan's resort hotels are not religiously constrained to eating pork, Palawan is well-rounded with various offerings such as fish and seafood, chicken, beef, and vegetables, among many others that may inspire chefs to create culinary creations that can be enjoyed any time of the day.

Another key component is safety and security. The former refers to a condition where someone or something must be protected from potential harm and its various causes. The latter is the implementation and measures to achieve the former whether by physical security or cybersecurity. Safety and security needs fulfill the hotel's obligation to provide a safe environment to both its clients and employees. These needs are more apparent in emergencies, particularly in times of force majeure. As such, the Business Continuity plans of various hotels, in collaboration with government agencies must be formulated, implemented, and established.

Palawan Resort hotels must explore the importance of Honest, transparent, and timely communication to help minimize customer uncertainty and anxiety and maintain their trust in a company's brand (Aripin & Agusiady, 2024). Lee et al (2016) opine that communication focuses on listening to the needs of customers, understanding the needs of the customers, setting and establishing expectations, and most importantly, constantly keeping customers informed. The impact of social media in building CS as a vital key to organizational success extends to diverse domains, including social, political, and commercial spheres, offering new avenues for engagement and communication (DeAtkine et al., 2023; Golder et al., 2023). Regarding information, Palawan resort hotels must provide learning, training, and development opportunities to their staff so that their guests will benefit from some of the more vital information about their tourist destination such as tour offerings, availability of amenities and various services, or establishments conveniently near the resort hotels' premises, if any. Should guests have urgent emergency medical needs, the staff must possess proactive, undivided attention and obligation to ensure their guests' health, wellness, safety, and security through accurate information and communication and coordination channels with nearby government agencies. Conducting SQCS surveys allows managers to identify and examine the current situation and make improvements (Miragaia et al., 2015).

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Figure 2: **CASA WISH First Choice Tourist Destination Framework.**

Source: Authors

Recommendations

As with all research, there are limitations to this study which provide avenues for future research. Several research implications and limitations emerged from this study. First, the study is limited to examining only 5 Four Star hotels located in Palawan. It means that limited to geographical area and data analyzed only considering 140 questionnaires. Also, the study has constraints and limitations that point to future research directions. This study does not account for post-purchase customer satisfaction, such as customer loyalty and word-of-mouth.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved throughout the study. The authors reported no potential conflict of interest and plagiarism was kept to a

minimum, if not, accidental. Any insights obtained by the researchers are for academic and new knowledge purposes only.

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